

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF GENERAL WELL BEING AMONG SCIENCE AND ARTS STUDENTS OF NIRMALA COLLEGE

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ABSTRACT:

The present study objective at assessing the comparative study of general wellbeing among science and arts student of different faculties. The sample of the study consists of 20 students (10 arts and 10 science) was taken on random basis. General wellbeing Score development by Dr. Devendra Singh, Puja Choudhary was used measure the General wellbeing of the respondent this scale has Total 50 items. Total item further divided into four dimensions related to wellbeing.

The result revealed as compare science and arts students had better level of general wellbeing but the difference between is not significant.

KEYWORDS:

GENERAL WELLBEING, EMOTIONAL WELLBEING, SOCIAL WELLBEING.

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INTRODUCTION

Wellbeing is the experience of health, happiness and prosperity. It includes having good mental health, high life satisfaction and a sense of meaning or purpose. More generally wellbeing is feeling. Wellbeing is something sought by just about everyone because it includes so many positive things-feeling happy, healthy, socially connected and purposeful but unfortunately wellbeing appears to be in decline (at least the U.S) and increasing your wellbeing can be tough without knowing what to do and how to do it. These are some of the reasons why founded the Borkelly wellbeing.

The recent years the subjects of wellbeing and happiness have all devoted considerable attention to their emerging fields fed partly by a growing body of evidence that people derive satisfaction from a variety of sources a hot merely from higher incomes. Much of the research though is very recent indeed with one economist. Speaking of lesson from a new Science in of summary, wellbeing and be defined as a positive mental state mutually embraced by some psychologists a mean of focusing attention on health and satisfaction with life rather on mental illness and its remedies. It has been adopted more widely by a range of social scientists and some policy makers.

General wellbeing is associated with such social qualities as confident optimism about the future. A sense of influence over one's own destiny and social competences that promotes satisfaction and supportive relationship with other people and not simply with an absence of diagnosed illness, disability or Dissatisfaction. It also critically involves the reliance needed to deal with hard

time as and when they occur. In policy terms it can be defined as the conditions which allow individuals and communities to flourish. It seems possible to connect the rise of academic and policy interest in wellbeing and happiness with the dilemmas of life in an affluent but highly risky society. Analysis of survey data has repeatedly shown that, once a society reaches a particular level of affluence. Further increase in material wealth produce very limited change in people self-reported happiness.

Wellbeing is more than just happiness in addition to being just telling satisfied and happy, wellbeing means developing as a person, being fulfilled and making a contribution to the community. Sociological research on the determinants of wellbeing. A society showed various indicators of societal wellbeing Leon and Baris (2010) review included a mix of 14 categories. All categories interact to determine the wellbeing of entire countries down to family units and individuals. These 14 categories include poverty, education, employment, income, health and wealth, shelter, natural environment, political participation, civil society, economic 3 participation, human life, national stability and sustainability, family wellbeing.

Definitions of General Wellbeing: The general well-being may be defined as the subjective feeling of contentment, happiness satisfaction with life's experiences and of one's role in the world of work, sense of achievement, utility, Belongingness, and no dissatisfaction or worry, etc. Evaluate objectively, hence the emphasis on the term "subjective" well-being. It may be maintained in adverse

conditions and conversely may be lost in favorable situation. It is related to but dependent upon physical/physiological conditions. The various definitions of general well-being as proposed by various stress, researchers are as follow:

Bradburn (1969) was among the first to define the concept of well-being and referred to it as "happiness". He introduced the notion of using mood to measure happiness. He focused on the positive and negative effect and stated that "an individual will be high in psychological well-being in degree to which he has an excess of positive over negative effect and will be in low in well-being in the degree to which negative effect predominates over positive".

Diener and Suh (1997) defined wellbeing as a concept that is characterized by three elements: pleasant effect, unpleasant effect and life satisfaction. They mentioned that affect refers to pleasant and unpleasant 4 mood and emotions, whereas life satisfaction refers to cognitive sense of satisfaction with life changes and stressors, their level of well-being may be influenced. Shin and Johnson (1978): defined general well-being as "a global assessment of a person's quality of life according to his own chosen criterion". Shah and Marks (2004) described well-being as "Well-being is more than just happiness. As well as felling satisfied and happy, well-being means developing as a person, being fulfilled, and making a contribution to the community.

Ryff's (1989): criticized the Bradburn's work as he did not define the basic structure of psychological well-being. Ryff's early work identified the autonomy, aspects that constitute well-being. These aspects are environmental mastery, positive relationship with others, and purpose in life, realization of potential and self-acceptance. Recently emphases have been placed on well-being like, ability to fulfill goal, happiness and life satisfaction (**Poillard & Lee, 2000**).

Nature of well-being Wellbeing is a multidimensional construct comprising of physical, mental and social components (Bhimwal, 2007). There are several cardinal characteristics of the well-being (**Diner, 1984**). It resides within the experience of the individual (**Campbell, 1976**). Well-being is a dynamic state characterized by a reasonable amount of harmony between an individual's abilities, needs, expectations, Environmental demands and opportunities (**Singh and Shaym, 2007**). Thus, it involves subjective satisfaction and individual pleasure depending upon psychological status of the individual and his environmental conditions (**Khan, 2007**). Notably absent from definitions of well-being are necessary objective conditions such as health, comfort, virtue or wealth (**Khan, 2007**). Well-being includes positive measures (Sharma, 2002). The well-being of the body, mind and emotions, the sense of ethics and morality, represent the concept of health, and not necessarily the absence of disease (**Jain, Sharma and Yadav, 2007**) It deals with the factors that differentiate slightly happy people from moderately happy and extremely happy people (**Sharma, 2002**). The field

covers the entire range of well-being from agony of ecstasy (**Sharma, 2000**). **Ryff and keys (1995)** include self-acceptance, positive relations with others, autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life and personal growth in well-being. A final hall-mark of well-being is that the field focuses on longer term states not just momentary moods (**Sharma, 2000**). Well-being researches are interested in relatively enduring feelings of well-being, not just fleeting emotions (**Diner, suh and Oishi, 1997**). 6

By concluding the nature of well-being, it can be said that it not only an absence of illness (**WHO, 1948**). **Jordan (1974) Shoben (1957) and Bremer (1996)** describe the well-being as intricate. Relationship between biological, social, emotional and spiritual ingredients which from footing for well-being.

AREAS OF GENERAL WELL-BEING

Physical well-being- Physical well-being is about being safe, sheltered and mental well-being. If we have good physical health, we will automatically experience better mental and emotional well-being on the other hand, mental stress and anxiety will put stress on internal organs, increase blood pressure, decrease immune function and upset chemical balances.

EMOTIONAL WELLBEING:

Every wellbeing is about how we feel, think and behave. Nobody feels blissfully happy thinks positive thought and behaves sensibly all the time but if you are in a pretty good state of mind generally it is much easier to enjoy life and cope with the challenges looking after your state of mind just as important as taking care of your body, yet better than our mental health. As soon as we feel a physical ache or pain, we generally try to do something about it but when we find ourselves low or stressed and anxious we tend to think it is just part and partial of life and don't do anything to improve the situation.

SOCIAL WELLBEING:

Social wellbeing is the extent to which you feel a sense of belonging and social inclusion. A connected person is a supported person in society, lifestyles, way of living together value systems, traditions and belief are all important to our social wellbeing and quality of life. With so many diverse cultures in our environment there are ample opportunity to be involved in groups. Programmers or multicultural wants involvement with our own culture can be very rewarding giving freedom to retain, Interpret and expert arts history, heritage traditions.

SCHOOL WELLBEING:

Children and relationships interactions with their family and communities contribute significantly to their sense of wellbeing understanding wellbeing in adolescents explores more about their school college experiences. As students move through their educational experiences Understanding the factors that shape their wellbeing contributes to the literature regarding the multitude of the way that school. Imparts students. Indeed, wellbeing can be related to self-esteem, cognitive function, personality

and mood, including positive effects such as happiness, vigor and morale and negative effects such as anxiety and depression.

MODLS

1. Self-acceptance High scorer

Possesses a positive attitude toward the self; acknowledges and accepts multiple aspects of self, including good and bad qualities; feels positive about past life. Low scorer: Feels dissatisfied with self; is disappointed with what has occurred with past life; is troubled about certain personal qualities; wishes to be different than what he or she is.

2. Positive relations with others

High scorer: Has warm, satisfying, trusting relationships with others; is concerned about the welfare of others; capable of strong empathy, affection, and intimacy; understands give and take of human relationships. Low scorer: Has few close, trusting relationships with others; finds it difficult to be warm, open, and concerned about others; is isolated and frustrated in interpersonal relationships; not willing to make compromises to sustain important ties with others.

3. Autonomy

High scorer: Is self-determining and independent; able to resist social pressures to think and act in certain ways; regulates behavior from within; evaluates self by personal standards. Low scorer: Is concerned about the expectations and evaluations of others; relies on judgments of others to make important decisions; conforms to social pressures to think and act in certain ways.

4. Environmental mastery

High scorer: Has a sense of mastery and competence in managing the environment; controls complex array of external activities; makes effective use of surrounding opportunities; able to choose or create contexts suitable to personal needs and values. Low scorer: Has difficulty managing everyday affairs; feels unable to change or improve surrounding context; is unaware of surrounding opportunities; lacks sense of control over external world.

5. Purpose in life

High scorer: Has goals in life and a sense of directedness; feels there is meaning to present and past life; holds beliefs that give life purpose; has aims and objectives for living. Low scorer: Lacks a sense of meaning in life: has few goals or aims, lacks sense of direction; does not see purpose of past life; has no outlook or beliefs that give life meaning.

6. Personal growth

High scorer: Has a feeling of continued development; sees self as growing and expanding; is open to new experiences; has sense of realizing his or her potential; sees improvement in self and behavior over time; is changing in ways that reflect more self-knowledge and effectiveness. Low scorer: Has a sense of personal stagnation; lacks sense

of improvement or expansion over time; feels bored and uninterested with life; feels unable to develop new attitudes or behaviors.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature is a systematic and explicit method for identifying the existing body of completed and recorded work produced by researchers.

Review is a process of examining and reviewing the selected resource with a purpose to provide the valuable direction and strength whole research process. It is also necessary as it provides the foundation for understanding the concepts in the light of various theoretical and empirical backgrounds. It is important to build the concept from work which is to be studied. Hence the review of literature was conducted of psychological wellbeing in relation to home environment, parental achievement and self-esteem and it has been organized accordingly.

Home environmental and psychological wellbeing

Parental Attachment and psychological wellbeing

Components of Psychological Wellbeing A person's overall life satisfaction, pleasant feelings, and low levels of negative emotions are all included in the broad and multidimensional concept of psychological well-being (Diener, Suh, Lucas, & Smith, 1999). Numerous essential elements of psychological well-being are well acknowledged in the literature.

Life Satisfaction: An individual's overall assessment of their life and their emotions of joy and fulfilment are referred to as life satisfaction (Diener et al., 1985). It is regarded as being essential to well-being since it is intimately correlate with one's sense of meaning and purpose in life (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000).

Positive Emotions: Affirmative emotions such as joy, excitement, and contentment are an important component of well-being because they promote a sense of happiness and fulfilment (Diener et al., 1997). Positive emotions also help to counteract negative emotions and stress, leading to improved overall well-being (Park & Peterson, 2006).

Low Levels of Negative Emotions: A person's wellbeing can be greatly impacted by negative emotions including anxiety, despair, and rage (Ryan & Deci, 2001). Therefore, maintaining low levels of negative emotions is crucial for psychological well-being since it enables people to sustain pleasant feelings and prevents adverse effects on mental health (Keyes & Lopez, 2002).

Autonomy: Autonomy refers to the ability to make decisions and act in a self-determined way (Ryf, 1989). Individuals who know-how high levels of autonomy are able to pursue their own goals and interests, which can lead to improved well-being (Waterman, 1993).

Positive Relationships: Positive interpersonal connections with loved ones, friends, and romantic interests are crucial for psychological health (Frederick & Loewenstein, 1999). These connections give people emotional support, a sense of community, and support for happiness and wellbeing

(Peterson & Seligman, 2004).

Personal Growth: Personal growth states to a person's on-going process of development and self-improvement (Ryff, 1989). This can involve learning new skills, exploring new interests, and developing new relationships (Lucas et al., 1996). Personal growth is an important aspect of well-being because it helps individuals to maintain a sense of growth and throughout their lives, fulfillment (Diener et al., 1999). In summary, life satisfaction, pleasant emotions, low levels of negative emotions, autonomy, positive connections, a sense of purpose in life, and personal growth are all important aspects of psychological wellbeing (Diener et al., 1999). These elements are connected and work together to advance general fulfillment, happiness, and well-being (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000).

Psychological well-being is a broad and multifaceted construct that refers to an individual's overall experience of positive emotions, satisfaction with life, and sense of purpose. The study of psychological well-being has been an active area of research in psychology for several decades, with the goal of gaining a deeper understanding of the factors that contribute to its development and maintenance.

One of the earliest and most influential models of psychological well-being was proposed by Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi (2000), who defined it as the result of two dimensions: positive emotion and engagement in meaningful activities. According to this model, individuals who experience frequent positive emotions and are actively engaged in activities that are meaningful to them are likely to have higher levels of psychological wellbeing.

Other researchers have expanded on this model by including additional dimensions of psychological well-being, such as positive relationships (Diener et al., 2010), personal growth (Linley & Joseph, 2004), and a sense of purpose (Ryff, 1989). These dimensions are considered to be critical to the development and maintenance of psychological well-being and are often taken into account in studies on this topic. Studies have found that both individual and environmental factors can impact psychological well-being. For example, research has shown that personality traits, such as openness and conscientiousness, are associated with higher levels of well-being (Costa & McCrae, 1980). Additionally, 16 personality traits, such as openness and conscientiousness, are associated with higher levels of well-being (Costa & McCrae, 1980). Additionally, environmental factors, such as access to green space and social support, have been found to have a positive impact on well-being (Oishi & Diener, 2001).

A growing body of research has explored the effects of mindfulness-based practices, such as meditation and yoga, on psychological well-being. These studies have demonstrated that these practices can have positive effects on mood, stress levels, and overall well-being (Brown & Ryan, 2003). Cognitive-behavioral therapies, such as

cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), have also been found to be effective in promoting well-being, particularly for individuals with depression and anxiety (Cuijpers et al., 2013).

Research has also shown that physical activity is positively associated with psychological well-being (Babyak et al., 2000). Physical activity has been shown to reduce stress, improve mood, and increase feelings of self-esteem and confidence (Lancaster & Strath, 2013). Exercise has also been found to be effective in the treatment of depression, with studies demonstrating its efficacy comparable to that of medication and psychotherapy (Babyak et al., 2000).

In summary, the literature on psychological well-being is extensive and growing. It is clear that psychological well-being is a complex construct that is influenced by a variety of individual and environmental factors, and 17 mindfulness-based practices, cognitive behavioral therapies, and physical activity can have positive effects on well-being. Nevertheless, much more research is needed to gain a full understanding of the nature of psychological well-being and the most effective strategies for promoting it. that intervention such as A. Radhakrishna Nair (2013): Stated that social skills were also predicted to be associated with a reduction in the experience of stress and have a strong relationship with growth and development. Thus, this study was designed to examine the role of social skills as a mediator between wellbeing. To test these two relationships data were collected from 220 school going adolescents. The basic tools used for this study is life skills assessment tool developed by RGNID, which measure social skills, thinking skills and coping skill and for measuring psychological wellbeing the Ryff Scale of psychological wellbeing. (RSPWB) scale was used. Analysis of the study indicates the social skills can predict psychological wellbeing. Implication for early school intervention to promote social skills and possible direction for further researches are discussed.

METHODOLOGY

PROBLEM: comparative study of psychological wellbeing among science students and arts students of Nirmala college Ranchi.

OBJECTIVE

- i) To find out the level of psychological wellbeing among science students' arts student of Nirmala College Ranchi
- ii) To find out the difference between science students' arts students in their psychological wellbeing

HYPOTHESE

- i) The level of psychotically wellbeing will vary in science and arts students
- ii) There will be no significant difference between science and arts college students in psychological wellbeing score

SAMPLE:

The sample of the study consists of 20 students (10 arts and 10 sciences). Sample of study was selected simple

random sampling from the college going students of the Nirmala College Ranchi. Their ages range was 18-21 years. Thus, the arts and science ratio were 1:1.

TOOLS

The following tools were used to achieve the goal of present study.

Personal Data Questionnaire:

This questionnaire was Prepared by the investigable on for collecting information about the respondents name, age, ethnicity, religion, gender, caste, Economic status etc.

General wellbeing score:

General wellbeing Score development by Dr. Devendra Singh, Puja Choudhary was used measure the General wellbeing of the respondent this scale has Total 50 items. Total item further divided into four dimensions related to wellbeing.

- Total 10 items in satisfaction wellbeing areas there were.
- Total 10 items in efficiency wellbeing areas there were.
- Total 10 items in Sociability wellbeing areas there were
- Total 10 items in Mental health wellbeing areas there were.
- Total 10 items in Interpersonal Relations wellbeing areas there were.

TABLE NO-1

Area of items

SL.NO	AREAS	TOTAL
1	Satisfaction wellbeing	10
2	Efficiency wellbeing	10
3	Sociability wellbeing	10
4	Mental Health wellbeing	10
5	Interpersonal Relation wellbeing	10
	TOTAL	50

Scoring: General wellbeing scale in self-reporting five-point scale Items of the scale are in statement from followed by five alternatives. The students have to tick one alternative against each scatternets. The score awarded for different alternative are given:

TABLE NO 2

Scoring Pattern

AGREE	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagreed
5	4	3	2	1

TABLE NO 3

Norms of interpretation of the row score (for each area)

SCORE	LEVEL OF PSYCHOLOGICAL WELLBEING
10-12	VERY LOW
12-16	LOW
16-43	MODERATE
43-48	HIGH
47-50	VERY HIGH

TABLE NO 4

Norms of Interpretation of the row score (for entire scale)

SCORE	LEVEL OF PSYCHOLOGICAL WELLBEING
50-58	VERY LOW
58-83	LOW
83-217	MODERATE
217-242	HIGH
242-250	VERY HIGH

DISCUSSION

Data Analysis and Discussion:

One of the important objectives of the present study was to examine the level of General Wellbeing of the college student to achieve this goal General Wellbeing Scale administered on students of Science and Arts.

TABLE NO 5

Number and percentage of students on different level of Group wellbeing.

GROUP	HIGH (231-275)		AVERAGE (168-230)		LOW	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
	1	5%	17	85%	2	10%

TABLE NO-6 (MEAN, SD, T-VALUE)

GROUP	ARTS	SCIENCE
MEAN	167.1	162.5
SD	25.9	23.40
T-RATIO	0.06	

TABLE NO 4.3 MEAN, SD, AND T-VALUE OF THE DAY SCIENCE AND ARTS STUDENTS.

SL.NO	DIMENSION	ARTS			SCIENCE			T-VALUE
		N	M	SD	N	M	SD	
1	SATISFACTION WELLBEING	10	28.5	43.92	10	32.3	13.21	0.31
2	EFFICIENCY WELLBEING	10	37.1	33.17	10	43.6	23.02	0.24
3	SOCIABILITY WELLBEING	10	30.3	61.37	10	25.1	17.45	0.24
4	MENTAL HEALTH WELLBEING	10	34.8	51.03	10	27.6	36.30	0.61
5	INTERPERSONAL RELATION WELLBEING	10	32.6	15.30	10	32.1	14.73	0.91

The Table No. 4.1 Show that out 20 students only of 1 student only of 1 student (5%) high level wellbeing scale, 17 students of average level of wellbeing are (85%) and 2 students is low percentage is (10%) wellbeing Scale.

CONCLUSION

1. 5% student had high level of general wellbeing.
2. Maximum students 85% had average level of general wellbeing
3. 10% students had low level of general wellbeing.
4. As compare science and arts students had better level of general wellbeing but the difference between is not significant.

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